

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DRUG PROMOTION LITERATURE BASED ON WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (W.H.O) GUIDELINES

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Objective: Drug promotional literatures (DPLs) are used as a promotional tool to advertise new drugs entering the market to doctors. The objective of the present study is to evaluate the accuracy of DPLs by using the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria.

Methods: An observational study was conducted from March to May 2024. The DPLs were collected from various departments at T.S. Misra University, Lucknow, India. The literature was evaluated based on 11 criteria laid down by the WHO.

Findings: Three-hundred DPLs were evaluated out of which Anti-Microbial, Miscellaneous (analgesics, anticancer, vaginal film, immuno-modulators, vaso-dilators, anti histamine, nasal-decongestants, anti-allergic, anti-diabetic, cortico-steroid, progesterone) and Cardiovascular drugs were the most promoted drugs. Brand name was present in all the 300 DPLs (100%) followed by Active principle of drug present in 289 DPLs (96.33%), Whereas Side effects, ADR, Precautions and Contraindications were absent in all the DPLs. Brand name was mentioned in all the DPLs (100%) similar to a study conducted in Iraq and India.^[19, 20] Generic name was found in 221 (73.66%) drug promotional literature. 9 out of the 11 WHO criteria were followed by only 1 DPL, 8 out of 11 criteria were followed by 3 DPLs and 7 out of 11 criteria were followed by 8 DPLs. None of the DPLs fulfilled all 11 required criteria of an ideal DPL as per WHO criteria.

Conclusion: Majority of DPLs satisfied only half of the WHO criteria for rational drug promotion and none of them fulfilled all the specified criteria. Irrelevant and exaggerated information in DPLs may mislead and result in irrational prescription. Therefore, physicians should critically evaluate DPLs regarding the current scientific evidence needed for quality patient care.

Keywords: Drug brochures; drug promotion; drug promotional literature.

“I Introduction”

Drug Promotional literature (DPL) refers to print the materials that are designed to popularize a Pharmaceutical brand, organization and/or its products and services. It can be created as a discrete product, or as a supplement to an event. Because of its concise nature, medical practitioners may sometimes depend on DPLs as the main sources of drug information. DPLs can be extremely helpful, when they are equipped with genuine information, as long as they do not mislead us or provide inadequate information about the drug. Hence, they must be critically evaluated. Therefore, pharmaceutical companies have to follow certain defined ethical guidelines at the national and international level for drug promotional endeavor. The World Health Organization (WHO) states that “all promotion-making claims concerning medicinal drugs should be reliable, accurate, truthful, informative, balanced, up to date and capable of substantiation and in good taste”.^[1]

A new drug is launched in the market every single day. Pharmaceutical companies use drug promotional literature (DPLs) as a prime marketing strategy to endorse their new drugs.^[2] DPLs are said to provide salient features of the drugs to convince medical professionals to prescribe the new drug.^[3, 4, 5] Often, it is the only source which treating physicians rely on for updating their preexisting knowledge about drugs^[6]. Unfortunately, physicians may have a negative impact of extensive marketing and may irrationally prescribe new products without confirming the authenticity of the claims, which can in turn result in adverse health consequences, e.g. failure of treatment, undesirable effects, rise in antibiotic-resistant microorganisms or an increase in the disease burden.

DPL influences the prescription of medical practitioners; they have to be critically analyzed for their content to prevent possible consequences. Medical practitioners should play a vital role in the critical evaluation of the information provided in a DPL before considering it as a reliable source of information and notify about the non compliant Pharmaceutical agencies to concerned authorities. Medical students need to adapt efficient prescription skills, interpretation of DPLs, and other sources of drug information before graduation. The manner of prescription by physicians relies upon the training they had during their practice. Recent upgradation in MBBS curriculum include self-directed learning skills, which will help in evaluation of DPLs by medical undergraduates in near future.^[7,8,9]

The combined efforts of medical practitioners, pharmaceutical companies and regulatory bodies can lead to effective control over unjustifiable content of DPLs. In turn, these efforts will guarantee that drug promotional literature is not a mere promotional activity but also a useful and appropriate source of information about pharmaceutical products. For rationale use of drugs, the WHO has laid down certain ethical criteria for medicinal drug promotion and has recommended pharmaceutical industries to implement these guidelines

“ II Methods”

An observational study was conducted by the Department of Pharmacology at T.S. Misra medical college and hospital, Lucknow, Uttar-Pradesh, India. DPLs in the form of flyer , brochures were collected from various outpatient departments which were available in the hospital through medical representatives. Collected DPLs were assessed as per the WHO criteria.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The data were expressed as percentage.

The following are the WHO criteria to be followed by pharmaceutical industries for the completeness of DPL ^[10]

1. The names of the active ingredients using either international non-proprietary names or the approved generic names of the drug
2. The brand name
3. Content of active ingredient per dosage form regimen
4. Name of other ingredients known to cause problems, i.e., adjuvant
5. Approved therapeutic uses
6. Dosage form or regimen
7. Side effects and major adverse drug reaction
8. Precautions, contraindications, and warnings
9. Major interactions
10. Name and address of the manufacturer or distributor
11. Reference to scientific literature as appropriate.

“III Results”

In the present study a total no of 300 Drug Promotion Literature (DPL) were analyzed according to the WHO criteria. *Table 1* represents the number of DPLs that fulfilled each parameter according to WHO criteria out of which, Brand name was present in all the 300 DPLs (100%) followed by Active principle of drug present in 289 DPLs (96.33%), Whereas Side effects, ADR, Precautions and Contraindications were absent in all the DPLs.

Table 1 - The WHO criteria fulfilled by Drug Promotion Literature

SERIAL NO	WHO CRITERIA BY DPL	MENTIONED NUMBER OF DPL	PERCENTAGE
1	Generic Name	221	73.66%
2	Brand Name	300	100%
3	Active Principle	289	96.33%
4	Approved Use	262	87.33%
5	Dosage Form	273	91%
6	Other Ingredient	1	0.33%
7	Side Effects and ADR	0	0%
8	Major Interaction	3	1%
9	Manufacturer a. Name and address b. Only Name	67 233	22.33% 77.66%
10	Precautions And C/I	0	0%
11	References	8	2.66%

Note: ADR: Adverse Drug Reactions; C/I: Contraindications.

Figure 1: Graph representing DPLs fulfilling WHO criteria.

SERIAL	CLASS OF DRUGS	NUMBER OF DRUGS EVALUATED
01	Anesthesia	17
02	Anti-Allergic drugs	11
03	Anti-Microbial drugs	50
04	CNS	13
05	CVS	38
06	Miscellaneous	41
07	Drugs For Rheumatoid Arthritis	8
08	GIT	28
09	NSAIDs	15
10	Ophthalmology	21
11	Psychiatry	29
12	Respiratory	6
13	Supplements	13
	TOTAL	300

Table II Number of drugs evaluated in each class of drug.

Figure 2 Graph representing number of drugs in each class

None of the DPLs revealed the price/cost of the drugs. *Figure 3*, represents the types of Pictures and images occupied on DPLs. DPLs depicted photographs of drug formulation, disease, organ, healthy/ depressed men and women, and others. All the DPLS were attractive readable and printed on good quality paper which was non-recyclable.

Figure 3 - Type of pictures displayed on dpls

TYPES OF PICTURES PRINTED ON DRUG PROMOTION LITERATURE

The present study concludes that 9 out of the 11 WHO criteria were followed by only 1 DPL, 8 out of 11 criteria were followed by followed by 3 DPLs and 7 out of 11 criteria were followed by 8 DPLs. None of the DPLs fulfilled all 11 required criteria of an ideal DPL as per WHO criteria.

“IV Discussion”

DPLs are used as a marketing trick to launch novel medications. DPLs are about new drugs or give new indications for old drugs. Drug manufacturers claim that their new products are better when compared to other products using these DPLs. These materials are often misleading. Therefore the drug promotions have become sale-centric rather than consumer-centric, which is a major drawback.

Anti-Microbial, Miscellaneous (analgesics, anticancer, vaginal film, immunomodulators, vasodilators, anti histamine, nasal decongestants, anti-allergic, anti-diabetic, corticosteroid, progesterone), Cardiovascular system were the most promoted drugs according to our study, indicating that drug companies are targeting these diseases. These findings are consistent with the study conducted in South India. ^[18]

Anti-microbial drugs are most widely sold drugs in India due to two major factors. First it is associated with the high incidence of infections caused by pathogens and secondly, due to indiscriminate prescription and irrational use of Anti-Microbial by physicians that has also contributed to Anti-Microbial resistance in the nation. In this study Brand name was mentioned in all the DPLs (100%) similar to a study conducted in Iraq and India. ^[19, 20] Generic name was found in 221 (73.66%) drug promotional literatures which similar to 84.5% observed in a tertiary care setting in South India. ^[21]

Approved uses were found in 262 DPLs (87.33%) which was consistent with a research conducted in DMIMS university of Maharashtra. ^[20] In our study most of the DPLs had dosage schedules and therapeutic indications, but essential details about adverse drug reactions, contraindications, or precautions were absent (0%). Most of the DPLs did not mention the safety feature of the drug promoted. Similar results were observed in other studies ^[22].

drug responses, medication interactions, precautions, and overdose was the most exempted part of DPLs. These findings, which are consistent with other studies carried out in other parts of India, found that fewer than 10% of the literature mentioned adverse drug reactions. ^[22, 23] This suggests that immoral drug promotion is widespread, which needs attention from all health authorities.

In our study, it was seen that none of the DPLs fulfilled all the criteria laid down by the WHO guidelines in our evaluation. A similar finding was reported in other studies. ^[24, 25, 26] This suggests that drug promotional companies are more involved in establishing a mercantile link with the physicians wherein moral and academic facet is compromised.

Evaluation of 300 drugs was done according to WHO drug promotional criteria but not a single DPLs satisfied all the enlisted parameters. Thus, we reach a conclusion that it is essential for Pharmaceutical companies to follow the W.H.O. criteria to ensure that legitimate information about drugs reaches the doctors. Also, it is essential for physicians to critically analyze, review and draw significant conclusions, before believing the claims made by the medical representatives or agents who promote their drugs, as these can mislead the physicians who trust the manufacturers' information on the drug promotional brochures. The health authorities must enforce strict regulations on DPLs to avoid such consequences.

DPL can pose as an irreplaceable source of information and can serve to upgrade the knowledge of the busy clinicians, helping them to remain updated with the latest developments in the pharmaceutical field. However, clinicians need to be aware that the pharmaceutical industry may use drug advertisements to influence prescription patterns and may be harmful due to the unawareness about the lethal outcomes.

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Conflict of interest

None

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